

A SURVEY ON IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES AND DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHM FOR BLOOD CELL CLASSIFICATION

Saranya vijayan1

MPhil Research Scholar,

Department of computer science

Avinashilingam Institute for home science
and higher education for women Coimbatore

641043

DrRadha Venkatachalam2

Professor

Department of Computer Science

Avinashilingam Institute for home science
and higher education for women Coimbatore

641043.

ABSTRACT:

The classification of blood cells is of great importance for the diagnosis of hematological diseases such as leukemia. In order to get the most effective treatment, the patient needs an early diagnosis. Early diagnosis of leukemia is likely to be treated successfully. Therefore it is very vital to have a support system. In this paper literature survey of some recent papers on blood cell classification using image processing techniques and deep learning algorithms have been reviewed. Deep learning algorithms have been proved to solve many challenging problems in the field of image processing. When compared with traditional machine learning algorithms, deep learning algorithms play a major role in terms of accuracy. Deep learning algorithms have brought many benefits to the medical field where they work with large amount of data. This paper

aims to analyze the existing image processing techniques for leukemic blood cell classification.

Keywords: blood diseases, leukemia, deep learning algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION:

According to a survey conducted in the US, In every 5 minutes at least one person is,300 people are expected to be diagnosed diagnosed with leukemia. An average of 177 with leukemia. The survey also states that approximately 156 people die out of blood cancer every day. The survey has found that blood cancers are expected to account for 9.4 percent of the deaths.

Leukemia is a type of blood cancer in which it would cause a rise in the number of white blood cells in the body. The

white blood cells in the body are responsible for fighting against infections. In case of people who are suffering from leukemia, the white blood cells can't fight against infections thus in turn causes low immunity and they are more prone to other diseases like fever. As a result of the rise in white blood cells, other organs in the body will start to get affected and it will result in less number of red blood cells to supply oxygen, enough platelets and also it may lead to drastic reduction of normal white blood cells that are responsible to fight against infections.

Leukemia can be caused due to exposure of certain types of radiations as well as chemicals or may be due to family history of leukemia. There are four types of leukemia as mentioned below.

- a) Acute lymphoblastic leukemia
- b) Chronic lymphocytic leukemia
- c) Acute myeloid leukemia
- d) Chronic myeloid leukemia

It is important to detect leukemia at an early stage because when it is not too large and it has not spread, it is more likely to be treated successfully. The effective treatment becomes more difficult if it spreads and it would reduce the person's chances of surviving.

Deep learning algorithms have been proved to solve many challenging

problems in the field of blood cell classification.

Deep learning algorithms have been divided into two categories. They are deep neural networks and restricted Boltzmann machine. Deep learning algorithms are proved to provide solutions for many challenging issues. It could be used for solving many challenging problems in areas of image processing, signal processing and speech recognition.

Convolution deep learning algorithm would directly take pixel values from the given input dataset and it would construct useful features by using its multilayer architecture.

The convolution deep learning algorithm has got three layers associated with it. They are convolution layers and pooling layers. The convolution layers have been assigned in the algorithm to extract features from the input image. Pooling layers take care of reducing the spatial size.

This paper has been organized into 5 sections. They are abstract, introduction, literature survey and conclusion.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY:

Prayag Tiwari a, Jia Qian b et al. (2019) have proposed convolution deep learning algorithm to detect blood subtypes. The metrics used by them was accuracy. In their research work they did

not classify the types of leukemia and that was their limitation.

Ahmed S. Negm et al. (2019) Osama A. Hassan et al. (2019) have identified a method known as K-means clustering. It was compared with LBG and KPE for blast detection in acute leukemia images. The K-means algorithm was superior to the LBG and KPE algorithms. In their research work the prediction of k value was difficult.

Friedhelm Schwenker et al. (2019) have analyzed methods such as SVM, MLP and CNN for their research work. They have used CNN classifier to explore the feasibility of deep learning approach to identify lymphocytes. They did not encode the position and orientation of objects in to their predictions.

T. T. P. Thanh, Caleb Vununu et al. (2019) have introduced Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based method to distinguish normal and abnormal blood cell images. Their network model was computationally expensive.

Ying Liu¹ and Feixiao Long et al. (2019) have introduced Ensemble model prediction method. Efficient for tackling the challenges. It is less robust and did not work well with small data sets. The metrics used were accuracy, precision and recall.

Sarmad Shafique et al. (2018) have investigated a method called as a pretrained DCNN was deployed for automatic detection and classification of

its subtype. They need huge amount of data to learn robust features.

NiranjanChatap, SiniShibu et al. (2018) have proposed iterative thresholding algorithm for the segmentation of noisy images. Their work had overcome the problems associated with segmentation of heavy noisy images, when compared with an algorithm known as watershed algorithm. Based on the prior information when thresholding approach was applied the algorithm has derived blood smear images.

S.Jagadeesh, Dr.E.Nagabhooshanam et al. (2018) have introduced an algorithm known as watershed algorithm for the segmentation of the bone marrow images. The algorithm has also performed the cancerous cell extraction from the blood image. Different features of the cells were also generated automatically. The feature quality of the cells was carried out by using some methods such as PCA and correlation. In their research work classification was done by the traditional classifier known as SVM.

JamaliFirmatBanzi, XueZhaojun et al. (2018) have adopted a framework for their research work. Their first step was image acquisition and the noises were removed using median filter followed by adjusting the contrast of the images. They have also done thresholding, fourier transform and log transform. They have applied mean filter as well as line plot.

Ms. Minal D. Joshi, Prof. Atul H. Karode et al. (2017) have adopted an efficient method in order to detect acute leukemia by making use of histogram equalization method and contrast enhancement. They have applied global thresholding,otsu method and after that feature extraction was done.They have used KNN for classification and the accuracy of their research work was 93%.

Emad A. Mohammed, Mostafa M.A. Mohammed et al. (2017) have adopted a method for the cell segmentation of leukemia cells. In their research work they have used otsu method by using an optimal threshold value.They have also performed canny edge detection.The dilation and erosion were also carried out and the pixels that are isolated were eliminated and they have derived a segmented nucleus.

SubrajeetMohapatra, DiptiPatraandetal. (2017) have examined a method known as color based clustering for the segmentation of the images of blood. They have done a comparison on the performances of some of the standard clustering techniques. The clustering techniques were k Means, FCM and FPCM. They have also used contour signature and hausdroff dimension for finding out the irregularities of the boundary of the nucleus. SVM classifier has been used to derive the results.

Sonal G. Deore Prof. Neeta Nemade et al. (2015)have proposed a method in which they have extracted the lymphocyte cells followed by extracting morphological indexes and then classification was done.

They have identified the single cells by enhancing the input image.The filter used was adaptive pre filtering.The second step of their research work was to identify the white cells by separating it from other components of blood. The third step was identifying the lymphocytes associated with the other white cells. The accuracy oftheir research work was 93.63%.

A method was investigated by Xiang li et al. (2018) for human blood cell classification, distinguishing white cells and red cells. Their method made use of deep convolutional neural networks.

An unique framework was identified by Hong Zhao et al. (2018) for classifying the heterogeneous shapes present in the images of blood by making use of deep convolutional networks for classification.based on, convolutional networks. Their approach has provided robust predictions to identify certain hematological diseases.

A new method was introduced by T markiewicz et al.(2016) in which they had exploited features in images of blood cells that have resemblance with geometry,texture and statistical analysis. They have focused on the feature selection and generation of features

W.qiang et al. (2015) have propose an algorithm named reinforcement learning algorithm for blood cell detection in order to classify the four different types of leukemia.

A strategy was developed by Mssnehadhakne et al. (2015) have

identified two techniques for blood cell classification. The methods were watershed algorithm and cluster combining along with filtering for the detection of cell.

Monika et al. (2014) has investigated another method for blood cell classification. Their method was watershed transform and morphological image processing technique. They have identified the affected white blood cells and applied their technique in matlab.

Mspariminder et al. (2015) have adopted a method using KNN and also they made use of other algorithm known as hough transform algorithm to detect and classify the abnormal cells due to leukemia.

Khot s et al. (2013) have used a classifier to detect leukemic cells. The classifier used was Support Vector Machine They have extracted the features from the images and had applied it to the classifier

Himali et al. (2015) have proposed that when compared with watershed transform, histogram equalizing methods and k means clustering, the shape based features are more accurate for counting leukemic cells. The accuracy of their method was 97.8%.

They made use of shape based features to detect different cells like basophils, monocytes, eosinophils and lymphocytes. Finally they have diagnosed the disease based on the immature cell count.

MrsTrupti et al. (2014) have identified a method called otsu method for the

segmentation of normal blood cells. They have used matlab to carry out their work.

C Vidya et al. (2015) have classified acute leukemia in four stages. The stages were pre processing, segmentation, feature extraction and classification. The size of the input image was resized and was converted by color conversion. Feature extraction is the process of transforming the input data in to the particular set of features. They have used SVM classifier to classify the leucocyte cells.

Tejasri et al. (2016) have adopted a segmentation method known as otsu. The feature extraction was done using contour signature. Based on the results of the contour signature leukemia was detected.

A.A rputhaet al. (2016) have identified a method based on k means clustering for the purpose of segmentation. They have done the feature extraction using local binary pattern and classification was performed using SVM.

HajaraAbdulkarimAliyu et al. (2018) have proposed a new method for finding out the red blood cell abnormality classification. In their research work they have compared the performance of SVM classifier with that of deep learning algorithm. They have used around 300 images to carry out their research work. They found out that for larger dataset deep learning algorithm works well in terms of accuracy when compared with SVM.

Ruchijogi et al.(2019) have proposed machine learning algorithms for the classification of blood cells. They have created the dataset into 9 classes and the features were extracted to create the feature matrix. They have done a survey on different classifiers and concluded that linear discriminate classifier worked well among all other algorithms. Their proposed classifier had an accuracy of 99% in all the classes.

Mehdi Habibzadeh et al. (2018) have investigated a new approach called deep learning approach for the white blood cell detection. They have worked under unfavorable climatic conditions also. In their work they have used different various inception and Resnet deep learning classification. They have mentioned that the future work could be done by using different deep learning algorithms such as convolution deep learning algorithm. Their research work could be extended by making use of their framework in the field of pathological analysis.

A method was developed by Prasadhi G. FalDesai et al. (2018) in which they have detected and classified leukemia in to different types. They have used k means clustering for segmentation. They have acquired an accuracy of 94.7% in classification. The drawback of their algorithm was that they had to pre assign the value of k. Their further research could be extended by focusing on that. The results of their research work can be assessed by using larger dataset.

T. Markiewicz, S. Osowski, et al. (2016) have proposed methods such

as support vector machine and naïve bays classification for the detection of leukemic cells. In their method they exploit the features of the image of the blood cells related to the texture, geometry and histograms. The drawback of their work was they had focused only on feature generation and selection.

M.C., Colunga, O.S., Siordia, S.J et al. (2017) have introduced Gaussian mixture using the EM algorithm. and Posteriori decision rule for blood cell classification. The advantage of their work was the accuracy over manual counting and they have used precise method for normal blood samples. The drawback was it could not be used for the detection of pathological diseases.

C.Reta, L.Alamirano, J.A.Gonzales, R.Diaz et al. (2015) have proposed Image grabbing , Fuzzy C clustering ,Sub imaging and Colour Conversion RGB to L^*a^*b . The major advantage of their method were the accuracy and measuring nucleus boundaries along with shape, colour and texture. The drawback of their method was they have classified lymphoblast into subtypes.

The above mentioned techniques and algorithms were some of the methods used by the researchers to figure out hematological diseases.

III. CONCLUSION:

Blood cell classification will be helpful in detecting life threatening diseases such as leukemia at an early stage so that the patients would be able to start the treatment as early as possible. The proposed research work aims in improving the accuracy of detecting such diseases by using convolutional deep learning algorithm, thereby eliminating the risk of inefficiency.

The deep learning algorithms have been proved for solving many challenging problems. In this research work deep learning algorithm called convolutional deep learning algorithm will be integrated with image processing techniques in order to detect and classify leukemia.

IV. REFERENCES:

1. NiranjanChatap, SiniShibu“ Analysis of blood samples for counting leukemia cells using Support vector machine and nearest neighbour”(IOSR-JCE) e-ISSN: 2278-0661,p-ISSN: 2278-8727, Volume 16, Issue 5, Ver. III (Sep – Oct. 2014), PP 79-87[2]S.Jagadeesh 1, Dr.E.Nagabhooshanam
2. , Dr.S.Venkatachalam., “Image processing based approach to cancer cell prediction in blood samples” International Journal of Technology and Engineering Sciences Vol.1 (1), ISSN: 2320-8007
3. T. Markiewicz, S. Osowski, B., Marianska,L., Moszczynski, “Automatic Recognition of the Blood Cells of Myelogenous Leukemia Using SVM”, Proceedings of International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, Montreal , Canada, July 31 –August 4, 2005,pp. 2496-2501.
4. W., Qiang, Zhongli, Z., 2011. “Reinforcement Learning, Algorithms and Its Application”,International Conference on Mechatronic Science, Electric Engineering and Computer,,Jilin, China, August 19-22, 2011, pp. 143-1146.
5. JamaliFirmatBanzi, XueZhaojun., “Detecting Morphological Nature of Cancerous Cell Using Image Processing Algorithms”International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 12, December 2013 1 ISSN 2250-3153
6. Ms. SnehaDhakne, Ms. Kumudini K. Borkute, Ms. Priyankalkhar., “Detection of cancer cell in blood samples using an Effective algorithm”(IJCESR) ISSN (PRINT): 2393-8374, (ONLINE): 2394-0697, VOLUME-2, ISSUE-6, 2015
7. Monika Mogra , 2,Vivek Srivastava., “ A Comprehensive Review of Analysis of Counting Blood Cells

- Using Different Image Processing Algorithms”International Journal of Engineering Science Invention ISSN (Online): 2319 –6734, ISSN (Print): 2319 –6726 www.ijesi.org Volume 3 Issue 6 | June 2014 | PP.29-31
8. Subhan, Ms. ParminderKaur., “ Significant Analysis of Leukemic Cells Extraction and Detection Using KNN and Hough Transform Algorithm”International Journal of Computer Science Trends and Technology (IJCT) –Volume 3 Issue 1, Jan-Feb 2015.
 9. Khot S.T, SnehaBhalekar, DivyaJaggi and Dolly Rani., “ An innovative approach in myelogenous leukemia detection using attribute analysis” (IJAE) ISSN (Print): 2278-8948, Volume-2, Issue-5, 2013.
 10. Ms. Minal D. Joshi, Prof. Atul H. Karode, Prof. S.R.Suralkar“White Blood Cells Segmentation and Classification to Detect Acute Leukemia”(IJETTCS) Volume 2, Issue 3, May –June 2013.
 11. Emad A. Mohammed, MostafaM.A.Mohammed, Christopher Naugler, Behrouz H. Far, “Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia Cell Segmentation From Microscopic Blood Images Using Watershed Algorithm and Optimal Thresholding”, 26th IEEE Canadian Conference Of Electrical AndComputer Engineering(CCECE), 2013.
 12. SosAgaian, Monica Madhukar, Anthony T. Chronopoulos, “Automated Screening System for Acute Myelogenous Leukemia Detection in Blood Microscopic Images”, IEEE Systems Journal
 13. SubrajeetMohapatra, DiptiPatraandSanghamitraSatpathy., ”Unsupervised Blood Microscopic Image Segmentation and Leukemia Detection using Color based Clustering”(IJCSIM) ISSN 2150-7988 Volume 4 (2012) pp. 477-485
 14. Sonal G. Deore Prof. Neeta Nemade.,”Image Analysis Framework for Automatic Extraction of the Progress of an Infection”(IJARCSSE)Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2013
 15. Himali P. Vaghela, HardikModi, ManojPandya, ManojPandya.,” Leukemia Detection using Digital Image Processing Techniques” (IJAS) –ISSN : 2249-0868 Volume 10 –No.1, November 2015
 16. Mrs. Trupti A. Kulkarni-Joshi, Prof. Dilip S. Bhosale.,“A Fast Segmentation Scheme for Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia Detection”(IJAREEIE)Vol. 3, Issue 2, February 2014 ISSN (Print) : 2320 –3765 ISSN (Online): 2278 –8875
 17. C.Vidhya, P.Saravanakumar, K.Keerthika, C.Nagalakshmi, B.Medonadevi.,” Classification of acute lymphoblastic leukemia in blood microscopic images using svm” (ICETSH-2015)ISSN: 2348 – 8549 .